

THE CONCEPT OF THE SONG AND ITS PLACE IN THE LIFE OF PEOPLE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783709>

Annotation: In this article, the concept of song and the meaning of songs, types of songs, the role of songs in human life, the importance of songs in the oral art of the Uzbek people, the classification of songs in the scientific works of scientists detailed information about.

Keywords: song, work, analysis, tradition, culture, human, people, history, writing, melody, society, community, population.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada qo'shiq tushunchasi va qo'shiqlarning mazmun mohiyati, qo'shiq turlari, qo'shiqlarning inson hayotidagi o'rni, qo'shiqlarning o'zbek xalq og'zaki badiiy ijodidagi ahamiyati, olimlarning ilmiy asarlarida qo'shiqlarning tasniflanishi haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qo'shiq, asar, tahlil, an'ana, madaniyat, inson, xalq, tarix, yozuv, kuy, jamiyat, jamoa, aholi.

Аннотация: В данной статье понятие песни и значение песен, виды песен, роль песен в жизни человека, значение песен в устном творчестве узбекского народа, классификация песен в научных трудах ученые подробные сведения о.

Ключевые слова: песня, произведение, анализ, традиция, культура, человек, народ, история, письменность, мелодия, общество, общность, население.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and in order to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual capacity, broad outlook and skillful use of information communications are required. Based on these

requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

The history of the Uzbek people and their musical performance is historically rich and colorful. He tried to show the place and status of the people in the social life, joys and sorrows through songs and melodies. In our opinion, he managed it wisely. The love of music, including singing, has permeated the people's blood, consciousness, and heart.

Since ancient times, man has expressed and has been expressing his reaction to the events taking place in the environment. These relationships are realized primarily through different actions, voices, passions, feelings, or a piece of music. Later, feelings were expressed by words, phrases, and dances. Later, people came up with woven stories explaining the creation of the world, nature, animals, plants, mountains, and water. Boys and girls weaved love songs. Legends and legends have appeared about the brave and brave young men of the tribe, about their extraordinary heroism. All these were popular among the people living in groups before the writing culture.[4]

It is known that the art of music is an inexhaustible source of aesthetic perception. It is a fascinating world that conquers the human heart and soul. A person always strives for beauty, loves it and enjoys it. They also follow these rules of beauty in their daily life and use them wisely. This process has been showing its influence in one way or another in the emergence of a reflexive way of life.

A song is a poetic musical genre in a broad sense; the most popular type of vocal music, based more on band form, as well as a general expression of poetic works intended to be sung. Songs belonging to folk art, created by composers and composers, in the direction of popular music are distinguished. depending on the origin, genre and content, ceremonial songs, public songs, urban, peasant, children's, household, military, lyrical, dance and other songs are distinguished. The melody is distinguished by the compactness of the diapason, the musical development based on the form of a stanza (or stanza-refrain), the common intonations of words and melodies in the system of tones, and the general expression of the development of the ideological-emotional content of the poetic text (as an artistic end). stands Another unique aspect of the song is the mutual proportionality of the poetic text and the melody forms, based on the structures of the same size (in the poem - stanza, in the melody - period).

The poetic texts of the song are distinguished by the precise composition, the expression of a certain complete thought in each verse. In the East, folk songs

have their own national characteristics, and in Central Asia they are called ir (jir), terma, olan, lapar, yalla. On the basis of these, the creativity of composers, modern song forms developed in the 20th century. The works of medieval poets (trouvères and troubadours in France, minnesingers in Germany, etc.) in European professional music. examples of the art of meistersingers, polyphonic Italian created in the Renaissance, German 1-1, French, songs in the homophonic style that became popular in the 17th-18th centuries, songs created by composers of the Romantic period, popular songs in the 20th century, pop songs and other stages of professional song development. Among the poets are P. Beranje, R. Burns, R. Khamzatov, V. Vusotsku and others, in Uzbekistan - Khamza, Khabibiy, Sabir Abdulla, Mirtemir, Chustiy, T. Tula, P. Mumin, N. Narzullayev, Mukhammad Yusuf, E. Vakhidov, J. Jabborov and others have made great contributions to the development of song poetry.[5]

Songs are connected with all aspects of the social life of the people, they are a unique art that has gone through certain stages of historical development and artistically reflects life in its own images depending on the level of human thinking. In the most popular ideologically and artistically high traditional songs of our people, the people's life, livelihood, dreams in their hearts, pain, joy, trust in the future, processes, tools, the form and meaning of life are expressed. Also, the powerful voice of fighting against violence, lack of freedom, and injustice was heard. The content of the songs was manifested through the artistic assimilation of the lyrical idea of the event, that is, through the attitude, feelings and mood to the events and events that occurred.

The real meaning of art is determined by the norms of social morality of a certain era of a person and his life, and beauty gives pleasure to a person through feeling. Songs, considered one of the main genres in Uzbek folk oral art, reflect people's life and moral norms through their own art. The inner world of people, the concept of thought, hopes, dreams and faith in the future are also expressed in a unique way.

Al-Farabi, who paid great attention to music education, the first musicologist in the world of Eastern music, the founder of music theory, a famous music theorist and practitioner from Central Asia, expresses many scientific and practical ideas on the issues of educating the young generation. The well-known scientist, philosopher, musicologist Jami wrote in his book "Risolai dar ilmi muzija" about composition, scale, and rhythm ratios. Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi also had great knowledge in the field of musical art, and his musical aesthetic views were reflected in works such as "Sabbai-Sayyor", [6] "Makhbub-ul-Qulub", "Khamsa".

In conclusion, Like all other nations, the Uzbek people have a rich musical heritage that goes back a long way, with rich national spiritual values, customs and traditions. Its music, tunes and songs determine the lifestyle, mentality and potential of the Uzbek people. This national musical heritage is extremely rich and diverse.

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